

STRENGTH ESTIMATION FOR FORMED PARTS OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE BY ACCOUNTING FOR FORMING PROCESS EFFECTS

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1 Introduction

CFRPs are expected to be used widely due to their excellent mechanical properties. But especially in the case of continuous fiber-reinforced composites, slow production rate prohibits more extensive applications. The use of thermoplastic resin-matrix composites and stamp forming is expected to achieve rapid creation of formed parts and overcome the disadvantage [1], [2].

Despite the advantage, stamp forming for continuous fiber-reinforced composites has such difficulties as wrinkling and fiber misalignment [3] as shown in Fig. 1. These problems result in significant and local degradation of formed parts performance characteristics. In other word, the effect of press forming process should be taken into account for the estimation of formed parts performance.

In this study, strength is examined for press-formed hemispheres from woven continuous CF/PPS composite sheet under various forming conditions.

Variation in fiber orientation resulted by stamp forming to semi-spherical shape is firstly examined, because misorientation of fibers to loading direction is supposed to effect most significantly on strength. The local change in shear angle of woven fabric resulted by forming was observed experimentally and numerical simulations using a pin-joint type element were also carried out. Both results were compared with each other. To verify the influence of the variation in fiber shear angle on the strength, the formed domes were fractured by internal pressure test and correspondence between the fracture origin and local shear angle variation was examined.

Subsequently it was checked whether the strength of formed domes was varied with press forming conditions in spite that formed shape and resulting fiber shear angle was the same. Press forming

parameters, e.g. blank holder force and die temperature, affect formability [4]-[6] and then the strength of formed parts are supposed to vary on those parameters as a result. Semi-spherical domes were formed under various blank holder forces and die temperatures, and their strength was evaluated by internal pressure test. It was clarified that the fracture pressure varied with blank hold force. On the other hand it was not affected by die temperature. Experimental evaluation of residual stress of fiber in a formed part was carried out using micro-Raman spectroscopy in order to prove the reason why the formed parts degraded with blank fold pressure.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

The material employed in this study was a commercial CF/PPS (Poly-Phenylene Sulfide) composite sheet (TEPEX dynalite207 BOND-LAMINATE GmbH [7]). It consisted of twilled carbon fabric impregnated with PPS resin, whose appearance was shown in Fig. 2. The structural, mechanical and thermal properties are detailed in Table 1.

Fig. 1 Hot stamping process

Table 1 Structural and mechanical properties of composite material

Description	Property
<i>Structural parameters</i>	
Weave	Twill 2/2
Yarn spacing	2mm
Layer/Thickness	[0/90] ₄ / 1mm
Volume fraction	45%
<i>Mechanical & thermal properties</i>	
Elastic modulus	55GPa
Tensile strength	710MPa
Melting temp.	553K
Glass-transition temp.	383K

Fig. 2 Photograph and schematic illustration of weave of CF/PPS sheet

Fig. 3 Geometry of semi-spherical punch, die and blank holder

2.2 Stamp Forming

Stamp forming experiments were performed by using an AC-servo press whose capacity is 1,100 kN (H1F110 Komatsu ltd.). Circular discs of 120mm in diameter were drawn into a hemisphere of 25mm in radius using a hemispherical punch and die with a blank holder, shown in Fig.3.

Prior to forming, sheets were heated at 573 K, which was over the melting temperature of the matrix resin of PPS. Then the blank was pressed up to bottom dead point which was set so that forming depth reached 25 mm and held for 30 sec. at the position. The blank holder force was maintained constant during forming by pneumatics. Temperature of the die and punch was monitored by thermocouples and controlled by imbedded heaters and cooling water tube.

Forming trials were conducted with various blank holder forces and die temperatures as shown in Table 2. Those parameters were chosen because they were considered to affect significantly on the formability and the resulting strength of the formed articles.

Table 2 Forming conditions used in trials

Blank-holder force	0, 4.9, 9.1, 15.3 kN
Die temperature	313, 333, 353, 373 K

2.2 Internal Pressure Fracture Test

Internal pressure was applied to the formed domes using an oil pump until failure with constraint at its

Fig. 4 Geometry of internal pressure fracture test of formed hemisphere

circumference of 60mm in diameter as shown Fig. 4. The formed hemispheres were subjected to bi-axial tensile stress as shown in Fig. 4. So the maximum pressure, P_{max} , was corresponded to the local weakest strength of the drawn blanks under bi-axial tensile stress.

3 Finite Element Modeling

A numerical simulation for local change in fiber angle (shear angle) induced by the forming process was carried out using PAM-FORM (ESI Japan, Ltd.). The blank sheet was modeled as fabric without resin, taking it into account that almost melting resin nearly bore the load arisen during the forming process. The fabric element used was a pin-joint model on which shear moduli and a locking angle were placed. The shear moduli and locking angle used in the simulation are listed in Table 3. Two different in-plane shearing moduli were employed before and after shear angle of the fabric exceeded the locking angle.

The blank was meshed with an element size of 2mm which was equal to the yarn pitch of the fabric, with a total of approximately 3,700 elements, as shown in Fig. 5. In order to compare the simulated data with the experiments, analyses were performed with the same blank-holder forces as those in the experiments. A friction condition was placed between the blank, punch, die and blank-holder.

Table 3 Element and parameters used in simulation

Element type	Fabric (pin-joint)
Locking angle	45 °
shear modulus before locking	0.1 GPa
Shear modulus after locking	1 GPa

Fig. 5 Finite element simulation model

4 Micro-Raman Spectroscopy Measurements

Raman spectra were measured using a microscopic Raman spectroscopy system coupled to an optical microscope (NRS-1000 JASCO Co.). By a 50X objective lens Ar⁺ laser light of 514.5 nm was focused onto a 1- μ m diameter spot to irradiate the fibers in drawn blanks.

The peak of 1580cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the scattered light was employed to evaluate the fiber stress. Like other reports [8], the peak shifted with stress and wave number ν was correlated to the applied fiber stress σ_f in a linear relation indicated by a dashed line in Fig. 6.

The measurements were made on three different locations as shown in Fig. 7, to see the local difference in the fiber residual stresses.

Fig. 6 Dependence of Raman shift on applied fiber stress

Fig. 7 Location of micro-Raman measurements

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 Variation in Shear Angle

5.1.1 Experimental Results

Latitude and longitude of the formed dome are henceforth denoted by φ and θ , respectively. φ is 90° at the top of the formed dome and 0° at the fringe.

θ is 0° in the direction along the weft and 90° along the warp. To see the change in fiber shear angle before and after forming, white orthogonal lines were drawn along the fibers on the blank sheet surface.

Fig. 8 Photographs of stamp-formed samples

Fig. 9 Fractured portion by internal pressure test

Fig. 10 Simulated results corresponding to experiments shown in Fig. 8

Fig. 8(a) and 8(b) showed the side view of the sample formed experimentally with blank holder force of 0 kN and die temperature of 373 K, from the viewpoint at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and 45° , respectively. From Fig. 8(a), the woven fabric located at $\theta = 0^\circ$ kept shear angle of 90° even after the forming. On the other hand Fig. 8(b) showed that trellising occurred at the fabric of $\theta = 45^\circ$. The variation in shear angle became larger with θ until θ reached 45° . Concerning the direction of φ the shear angle maintained a right angle at $\varphi = 90^\circ$ and varied with decrease of φ . So the largest variation of shear angle took place at $\theta = 45^\circ$ and $\varphi = 0^\circ$ i.e., in the direction at an angle of 45° to the weft or warp at the bottom circumference of the drawn hemisphere. There the shear angle varied from 90° to 60° or 120° by forming process.

5.1.2 Fracture Origin of Internal Pressure Test

Fig. 9 shows the cracking portion after an internal pressure test. Fracture origin was located at the bottom circumference of $\theta = 45^\circ$ and $\varphi = 0^\circ$, as shown in Fig. 9. The location coincided with the region above mentioned where the largest variation of shear angle occurred. The crack was generated by the stress acted in the direction of latitude φ , σ_φ . At $\theta = 0^\circ$ direction of the weft coincided with that of σ_φ , where the variation in shear angle nearly occurred. On the other hand the weft was angled at an angle of $\pm 30^\circ$ from σ_φ at the fracture origin. This suggested that region where the weft deviated from σ_φ at the largest angle, became the fracture origin. Because strength of CFRP significantly depends on fiber alignment with applied stress, the results elucidated that the strength of press-formed CFRP parts was affected by forming process and varied locally according to variation in shear angle.

5.1.3 Finite Element Analysis of Shear Angle

Fig. 10 showed the obtained results by simulations, which were illustrated corresponding to the experimental results shown in Fig. 8. Lines displayed on the simulated results were corresponded to those drawn on the experimental blanks. Compared Fig. 10 to Fig. 8 they matched well in appearance.

In Fig. 11 simulated results of shear angle at $\varphi = 20^\circ$ and 45° against θ were shown in detail, together

with the experimental results. The vertical axis indicates angular variation in shear angle from the initial shear angle of 90°. There was some disagreement between the simulated results and the experimental results. Because the formed shape was hemispherical, simulated results should be symmetric with $\theta = 45^\circ$ as the graphic in the upper of Fig. 11 but the detail results in Fig. 11 showed asymmetrical distribution. This discrepancy might result from the relative large mesh size of the blank or from un-uniformity in thickness around the flange due to overlap of wrinkles. If the simulated results were in a symmetric manner, they will agree with the experimental results with reasonable accuracy. The simulation here assumed that matrix did not

Fig. 11 Variation in shear angle around 1/4 circumference at $\varphi=20^\circ$ and 45°

function during hot forming and the simulated results explained the experimental results with reasonable accuracy. So it is possible to say that properties of fabric, i.e., locking angle and shear moduli, play an important role in the prediction of shear angle and resulting local strength after press forming.

5.2 Effect of Blank-holder Force and Die Temperature on Strength

5.2.1 Variation in Shear Angle with Forming Conditions

If strength of formed parts can be determined only by shear angle after forming, prediction of strength of formed parts is easy to do using simulation for shear angle. On the other hand, forming conditions affect formability of blank seriously, and resulted degradation in strength of formed blank due to poor formability will probably occur. Blank holder force and die temperature are the typical parameters which much affect forming behavior and so their effect on strength of formed parts was examined. Before effect of forming conditions, i.e., blank-holder force and die temperature, on strength is discussed, it is necessary to see whether shear angle differs depending on forming conditions, firstly. If shear angle varies with forming conditions even

Fig.12 Variation in shear angle around 1/4 of formed semi-spheres under various press conditions

though formed shape is the same, its effect on the strength is superposed on effects of forming conditions.

To see whether shear angle varies on forming conditions, shear angles of the semi-spherical domes formed under the various forming conditions were measured

Fig. 13 Fracture pressure of semi-spheres formed under various blank holder force at die temperature of 333 K

Fig. 14 Fracture pressure of semi-spheres formed under various die temperature with blank holder force of 4.9 kN

In Fig. 12, shear angles around a quarter circumference at $\varphi = 20^\circ$ were shown. The measured shear angles were almost the same except the result of die temperature of 333 K and blank holder force of 4.9 kN. In the case of die temperature of 333 K and blank holder force of 4.9 kN, the shear angle at $\theta = 45^\circ$ was a little smaller but shear angle at the other angle of θ was almost the same as those of the other results. From the results when the same shape was formed, it is not necessary to take the difference of shear angle into account even though different forming conditions were employed.

5.2.2 Internal Pressure Fracture Test Results

Effect of blank holder force

In Fig. 13, fracture pressures, P_{max} were shown and those were obtained from domes formed under various blank holder forces of 0 to 15.3 kN and a constant die temperature of 333 K. From Fig. 13 it was seen that fracture pressure P_{max} decreased with blank holder forces.

Effect of Die Temperature

On the other hand, in Fig. 14 the result obtained from the experiments where blank holder force was constant of 4.9 kN and die temperature was 313 to 473 K. Unlike the case shown in Fig. 13, fracture pressures P_{max} nearly changed with die temperatures.

From the above it was proved that blank holder force must be taken into account when strength of formed blank is estimated. But die temperature is not necessary to be taken into account for prediction of formed blank strength.

5.3 Evaluation of Fiber Residual Stress

From the results shown in section 5.2, it came clear that strength of formed blanks varied depending on forming conditions. It is assumed because such micro defects as fiber residual stress, interfacial debonding and delamination may take place accompanied with the forming process.

The residual stress caused in fibers was evaluated by using microscopic Raman spectroscopy and difference of residual stress depending on fiber locations in a formed blank was examined.

The result obtained from a hemisphere formed under blank holder force of 0 kN and die temperature of 373 K was shown in Fig. 15. In the figure A, B and

C indicated the locations of measured fibers. A is the top of a formed dome ($\theta = 0^\circ$, $\varphi = 90^\circ$). B and C were the points located at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and 45° on the circumference of $\varphi = 0^\circ$, respectively. Fiber stresses at the each point were obtained from three different adjacent fibers. For comparison fiber stresses obtained from the fibers in an as-received plate before forming were plotted in the same figure.

The fiber stresses of as-received sheet showed little dispersion and on the other hand those from a formed blank varied widely. Although dispersion of the fiber stresses obtained from a formed blank was rather large, it was proved that almost all the stresses were tensile. The tensile stresses generated in some fibers were about 1 GPa and large enough to decrease the stress at break. Because of large variations in the evaluated stresses, the measured results provide no insight into local difference of fiber residual stress. To clarify the local stress distribution precise measurements will be carried out in future.

6 Conclusions

To predict strength of formed CF RTP parts, it is necessary to take effect of forming process on strength into account. In this study, a composite

Fig. 15 Residual stress in fibers of a formed blank on various locations, evaluated by micro-Raman spectroscopy

blank sheet of weaved continuous carbon fiber fabric was formed semi-spherical shape and it was

examined how variation in shear angle caused by forming process and forming conditions effect on strength of the formed blank. Strength of the formed blank was evaluated by internal pressure fracture tests. Also residual stresses of fibers in the formed blank were evaluated using micro-Raman spectroscopy in order to clarify the reason why degradation in strength occurred with blank holder force despite the same shear angle. The results obtained are summarized as follows:

1. Variation in shear angle took place during forming process and the variation was different on locations. The variation in shear angle caused local distribution of strength in the formed blank.
2. From numerical simulations, such properties as locking angle and shear moduli of fabric play an important role on prediction of variation in shear angle during hot forming.
3. Even though shear angles were the same, strength of formed blank varied depending on forming conditions. Blank holder force affected the strength of the formed blank but die temperature nearly affected.
4. Evaluation of stresses of fibers in a formed hemisphere using micro-Raman spectroscopy revealed that considerable tensile residual stresses were generated locally and they were large enough to affect fiber break stress.

In future causes of strength degradation will be examined more precisely by observation of residual stresses and micro-damages.

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References

- [1] J. Yanagimoto and K. Ikeuchi "Sheet forming process of carbon fiber reinforced plastics for lightweight parts". *CIRP Annals – Manufacturing Technology*, Vol. 61, pp247-250, 2012.

- [2] T.Yoneyama, T. Teraoka, K. Masuzawa, Y. Nishihara, S. Nagashima and H. Yoshida “Press forming of carbon-fiber reinforced thermoplastic sheets”. *J. of the Japan Society for Technology of Plasticity*, Vol. 53, No. 613, pp 2-22, 2004. (in Japanese)
- [3] A.G. Prodromou and J. Chen “On the relationship between shear angle and wrinkling of textile composite preforms”. *Composites Part A*, Vol. 28A, pp 491-503, 1997.
- [4] J.S. Lee, S.J. Hong, W.-R. Yu and T.J. Kang “The effect of blank holder force on the stamp forming behavior of non-crimp fabric with a chain stitch”. *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 67, pp 357-366, 2007.
- [5] M.T. Tahaye, H.R. R. Daghyani and S. Fariborz “Finite elemrnt analysis of thermoplastic composite plates in forming temperature”. *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 66, pp 306-313, 2006.
- [6] S. Davey, R. Das, W.J. Cantwell and S. Kalyanasundaram “Forming studies of carbon fibre composite sheets in dome forming processes”. *Composites Structures*, Vol. 97, pp 310-316, 2013.
- [7] <http://www.bond-laminates.com/en/tepexr-materials/tepexr-properties.html>
- [8] T. Miyake, S. Kokawa, N. Ohno and S. Biwa “Evaluation of Time-dependent Change in Fiber Stress Profiles during Long-term Pull-out Tests at Constant Loads Using Raman Spectroscopy”. *J. Materials Science*, Vol.36, pp 5169-5175, (2001).